

The sounds of Wilderplace, a web based puzzle-adventure game

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ABSTRACT

Wilderplace[1][2] is an upcoming puzzle-adventure game made in the web browser and soon to be released as an Electron app on Steam. This talk is about how the game’s whimsical soundscape came to be. Wilderplace’s in-game audio is entirely mixed, synthesized and dynamically sequenced using the Web Audio API and a unique, experimental medley of supporting JavaScript and Web Assembly modules including `tonal.js`[3], the reactive streams library `@most/core`[4], `Tone.js`[5], `webdx7`[6] and a DSP module generated using the Faust IDE[7].

Through a series of anecdotes about aspirations, challenges and realizations experienced during development, in this talk I’ll sketch out an overview of key technical decisions that were made and the audio system that emerged in the end. In closing I’ll share some reflections and possible directions for further exploration.

1. BACKGROUND

Wilderplace is a story driven puzzle-adventure game with turn-based gameplay. The player takes on the role of a shaman who’s been summoned by “the warden of the divine garden” to restore balance in a world that has fallen into agony and disarray.

2. THE WILDERPLACE AUDIO ENGINE

2.1 Synthesis

All synthesis is performed in real time by several dozen instances of `webdx7`, with the exception some white noise generated by `Tone.js`.

2.2 Sequencing and scheduling

Sequencing is done entirely in an audio thread via the `AudioWorklet` interface using `@most/core` reactive stream generators and composition functions.

Scheduling is handled by a custom implementation of the `@most/core`’s flexible and extensible scheduler interface. The scheduler is directly driven by the `currentTime` variable of `AudioWorkletGlobalScope`.

2.3 Stream composition

The music and sound effects in Wilderplace are driven by a creative mess of stream composition functions that transform and integrate streams of game state updates with streams of both pre-recorded and generated musical event data. All of this happens on the audio thread in the context of an `AudioWorkletProcessor`.

Typical examples of stream data include:

- generated and pre-recorded musical data such as note events and pitchclass sets
- game state updates¹ events and associated data sent from from the main thread
- transformed, intermediate representations derived from lower level source streams, such as streams signalling complex and specific occurrences in the game
- higher order streams containing entire sequences of musical events.
- streams of control data, e.g. to turn parts on and off
- “aggregate” streams containing information about currently active notes that feed back into upstream or downstream modifiers

2.4 Importing pre-recorded musical sequences and audio related metadata

The XML-based `dawproject`[9] format is used to get compositions of note sequences, pitchclass set data, DX7 sysex presets and mix-related metadata recorded and arranged in Bitwig Studio into the game engine.

2.5 Mixing and audio effects

`Tone.js` is used for mixing and to setup a graph of Web Audio nodes (partially driven by the track metadata from the `dawproject` file). Most of these are standard nodes, but a noise gate made with the Faust IDE helps reduce pileups of high frequency noise from layers of DX7 generated sounds.

3. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Wilderplace is an original creation of Saman Bemel-Benrud, who invited me to work on the audio for this game and granted me a huge amount of technical and creative freedom to explore interesting approaches to the audio implementation. Tom Lubanovic is our level designer and world builder and shared creative and organizational direction. I’m grateful to both of them for including me on this project, for their support and insightful feedback, for sharing their creative energy and their dedication to it through. I’m also grateful for the support of Tylor Steinberger and Michel Buffa for helping me work through challenging technical issues. In addition, none of this would have been possible without the work of countless of open source contributors. Lastly I’d like to thank all of the loved ones in my life who supported me in my decision to dive into this project.

¹Wilderplace’s state game state evolves deterministically, and is implemented using an event-like architecture and a custom LISP-like expression language[8].

4. REFERENCES

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